

Invitation to create Global Monsoon Time Scales for world monsoon regions&countries

(Do simple climate researches on your monsoonal climate, create your regional, country, local climate time scales and become renowned as scientists.)

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ABSTRACT: There are many global monsoon systems, regional monsoon systems and sub-regional monsoon systems in the world. In fact each and every region and country has it's own monsoon winds. Monsoon Time Scales for all world regions and countries are proposed and designed by me to study their regions and countries. So world scientists can make the Monsoon Time Scales and study their monsoon systems. Find out and study them just prefixing a monsoon region or country name to Monsoon Time Scale and searching in all websites just like as AUSTRALIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE. Scientists who make those Monsoon Time Scales have trouble in making it, kindly take my assistance in making the Monsoon Time Scales. Email id to contact me is gangadhar19582058@gmail.com. I will create model Monsoon Time Scales and send the same to them for study. For this, they must send the list of events of climate just like dust storms, monsoon low pressure systems etc. last 140 years since 1880 formed over their country's regions in the procedure cited below reference. In addition to this, a certain amount should be sent for expenses. You need to design the computer model later.

KEY WORDS: Global Monsoon Time Scales, Indian Monsoon Time Scale.

Introduction:

Global Monsoon Time Scale – a Chronological sequence of events arranged in between time and weather with the help of a scale for studying the past's, present and future movements of monsoon of a country and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problem and natural calamities. Prepare a global monsoon time scales having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th of a required period comprising of a large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The main weather events if any of the country's weather have been entering on the scale as per date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale of a region or country in this manner continuously, we can study the past, present and future movements of monsoon of a region or country.

Regional Monsoon Time Scales

- *Australian Monsoon Time Scale
- *North American Monsoon Time Scale
- *South American Monsoon Time Scale
- *Indian Monsoon Time Scale
- *European Monsoon Time Scale
- *East Asian Monsoon Time Scale
- *North African Monsoon Time Scale
- *South African Monsoon Time Scale
- *South Asian Monsoon Time Scale

SubRegional MonsoonTimeScales

- *North East Monsoon Time Scale
- *SouthWest Monsoon Time Scale
- *EastAfrican Monsoon Time Scale
- *WestAfrican Monsoon Time Scale
- *IndoAustralian Monsoon Time Scale
- *AsianAustralian Monsoon Time Scale
- *MalasianAustralian Monsoon Time Scale
- *NorthAustralianMonsoon Time Scale
- *AustralianIndonesianMonsoon Time Scale

CountryMonsoon Time Scales

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Formation:

The aforesaid Global Monsoon Time Scales are chronological sequences of events arranged in between time and climate with the help of a scale for studying the past's, present and future movements of the aforesaid monsoon regions or all world countries and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problem

and natural calamities. Prepare those Global Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th of a required period comprising of a large time and climate have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale.

Management:

The main weather events if any of the country have been entering on the scale as per date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale of a country in this manner continuously, we can study the past, present and future movements of monsoon of a region or country.

Model scale:

I have conducted many researches on the Indian monsoon and invented the Indian Monsoon Time Scale in 1991 which can help to study the past, present and future movements of the Indian monsoon and its weather conditions and natural calamities.

Construction: Prepare the Indian Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th (or from 1st April to next year March 31st) of 139 years from 1888 to 2027 (or a required period) comprising of a large space and time have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale.

Management: The monsoon pulses in the form of low pressure systems over the Indian region during the period from 1888 to till date have been taken and entering on the scale in stages by 1 for low, 2 for depression, 3 for storm, 4 for severe storm and 5 for severe storm with core of hurricane winds pertaining to the date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale in this manner continuously, we can see and study the past, present and future movements of the India monsoon..

Study&results: During the period of 1871-2015, there were 19 major flood years:1874, 1878, 1892, 1893, 1894, 1910, 1916, 1917, 1933, 1942, 1947, 1956, 1959, 1961, 1970, 1975, 1983, 1988, 1994. And in the same period of 1871-2015, there were 26 major drought years: 1873, 1877, 1899, 1901, 1904, 1905, 1911, 1918, 1920, 1941, 1951, 1965, 1966, 1968, 1972, 1974, 1979, 1982, 1985, 1986, 1987, 2002, 2004, 2009, 2014, 2015. Depending on the data mentioned above, it is interesting to note that there have been alternating periods extending to 3-4 decades with less and more frequent weak monsoons over India.

By 1888, the line of path of the Indian monsoon was started over the month of June and travelled to 1900's in steep descending direction over the June, July, August, September. As a result, there were heavy rains and floods in most years. During 1900-1920's, it was falling over the months of August and September in the shape of concave direction. As a result, it rained only two months instead of four months monsoon season and causing low rainfall in many years. During 1920-1965's, it was rising again over the months of July, August and September in the shape of convex direction. As a result, it rained only three months instead of four months monsoon season and resulting good rainfall in more years. During 1965-2004's, it was falling over the months of August to mid-august in the shape of deep sloping direction, In this 4 months monsoon season, the line was travelled just over two months for a short period only. As a result low rainfall and droughts in many years. From 2004, the line of path of the Indian monsoon seems likely rising over the months of July and to June in future in the shape of upper ascending direction and will be resulting heavy rains & floods in coming years during 2004-2060.

Scientific theorem:

The cause is unknown but the year to year change of movement of axis of the earth inclined at 23½ degrees from vertical to its path around the sun does play a significant role in formation of clusters, bands & paths of the Indian Monsoon and stimulates the Indian weather. The inter-tropical convergence zone at the equator follows the movement of the sun and shifts north of the equator merges with the heat low pressure zone created by the rising heat of the sub-continent due to direct and converging rays of the summer sun on the India Sub-Continent and develops into the monsoon trough and maintain monsoon circulation.

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INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE

